

CASES

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Abstract: A conjunction is a grammatical form that shows the relationship of a noun or noun to other words. Being a noun, it indicates that it is subordinate to another word in a compound or sentence.

Key words: nominative, accusative, locative, ablative and genitive cases.

Аннотация: Союз – это грамматическая форма, показывающая отношение существительного или существительного к другим словам. Будучи существительным, оно указывает на то, что оно подчинено другому слову в сложном слове или предложении.

Ключевые слова: именительный, винительный и родительный падеж случаи.

Annotatsiya: Kelishik — ot yoki otlashgan soʻzning boshqa soʻzlar bilan aloqasini koʻrsatuvchi grammatik shakl. U ot shakli ekanligi holda, birikma yoki gap tarkibida uning boshqa soʻzga tobe'lanishini koʻrsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Kelishiklar bosh, qaratqich, tushun, jo'nalish, o'rin-payrt, chiqish.

A grammatical case is a category of nouns and noun modifiers that corresponds to one or more potential grammatical functions for a nominal group in a wording. In various languages, nominal groups consisting of a noun and its modifiers belong to one of a few such categories. For instance, in English, one says see them and they see me: the nominative pronouns they represent the perceiver and the accusative pronouns me/them represent the phenomenon perceived. Here,

nominative and accusative are cases, that is, categories of pronouns corresponding to the functions they have in representation.

U kechasi bilan televizor ko'rib chiqdi. [3;195]

***The cat** chased the mouse. [2; 123]*

The nominative case is a grammatical case used in many languages to indicate the subject of a sentence. In languages with a nominative-accusative alignment, the nominative case marks the subject of a verb, while the accusative case marks the direct object. In English, the nominative case is seen in pronouns like "**I**," "**he**," "**she**," "**we**," and "**they**," which are used as subjects in sentences.

Bolalarning quvnashini ko'rib bahri dilim ochildi . [3; 198]

*I kicked **the ball**. [1;149]*

In languages with accusative cases, **nouns** and **pronouns** change their form to indicate that they are the direct object of a verb. Here are examples of the **accusative case** in different languages:

Men kitobni o'qidim[3; 199]

*- "**The car of my friend**" [5; 4]*

In grammar, the genitive is the **grammatical case** that marks a word, usually a noun, as modifying another word, also usually a noun—thus indicating an attributive relationship of one noun to the other noun genitive can also serve purposes indicating other relationships.

U she'rlarini chop ettirish niyatida matbuotga yo'l oldi [6; 203]

*I gave the book **to her** [1; 177]*

Dative case: nouns pronouns are grammatically in the "**dative case**". The case indicates the link between a noun or pronoun and other words in the phrase.

Men maktabda dars qildim. [3; 197]

*She walked away **from** the park. [1; 63]*

The ablative case is used in several instances. A noun in the ablative case can

usually be translated with the meanings '**by**', '**from**', or '**with**'. Certain prepositions or verbs take the ablative case, such as '**pro**', '**e**', '**ex**', '**cum**' and '**abutor**' and then the translation will be the meaning of the preposition instead.

Hoshimjon bosh olib uyidan Toshkentga ketdi. [6; 113]

*I am **at** (in) the library, you can find me easily [2; 105]*

In grammar, the locative case is a grammatical case which indicates a location. It corresponds vaguely to the English prepositions "**in**", "**on**", "**at**", and "**by**". The locative case belongs to the general local cases, together with the lative and separative case.

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